

Palenque's Temple of the Inscriptions

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The Temple of the Inscriptions at the archaeological site of Palenque, Mexico, is a monumental stepped pyramidal structure that during the Maya Classic period contained the chamber mausoleum of Lord K'inich Janaab' Pakal I, a Classic Maya sovereigns who regnal period counts among the longest among all dynasts. The lid of the monolithic shrine that harbors his mortal remains likens the dead aristocrat with the Maize God during his resurrection, cycling along a cosmic central ductus represented as a foliated world tree. Having been commissioned already 25 years by Janaab' Pakal himself prior to death in 683 CE, the inner sanctuary was finished five months after the monarch's passing and was used as a major ancestral shrine until the time of the Classic Maya collapse during the eight and ninth century CE.

Date Range: 650 CE - 800 CE

Region: Western Maya sphere

Region tags: Maya, Mexico

The Western Maya sphere during the Late Classic Period (600-800CE).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ruz Lhullier, Alberto. 1973. El Templo de las Inscripciones, Palenque. Colección Científica 7, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Mexico City.
- Source 2: Chinchilla, Oswaldo. 2006. The Stars of the Palenque Sarcophagus. RES 49/50:40-58.
- Source 3: Greene Robertson, Merle. 1983. The Sculpture of Palenque. Vol. I. The Temple of Inscriptions. Princeton University, Princeton.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Palenque>
- Source 1 Description: This source describes the archaeological site of Palenque, where the Temple of the Inscriptions was erected.
- Source 2 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Temple_of_the_Inscriptions

– Source 2 Description: This source describes the history and significance of the Temple of the Inscriptions, Palenque

– Source 3 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/K%CA%BCinich_Janaab%CA%BC_Pakal

– Source 3 Description: This source describes the ancestral veneration of one of the major Maya rulers of the Classic period.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1948-2023

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Arqueológico Palenque

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Rock face

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
– Yes

- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

- ↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: Stepped temple pyramid

- ↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

- ↳ A group of features:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: the semi-divine ancestor

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– I don't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Council of elders
– King or emperor
– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:
– Yes

↳ Groups:
– Priests
– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:
– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: Passing of ruler

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Construction of his mortuary shrine commissioned by the ruler

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

–Type: pedigree of Palenque's dynastic succession

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– Yes

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

↳ Space underneath the structure

– No

- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: none

- ↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:
 - I don't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- Yes

- ↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
 - Square meters: 2240

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 35

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Height, meters: 35

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: pigment

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Cut stone slabs

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– No

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: none

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:
– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:
– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– Yes

↳ Interment:
– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:
– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:
– No

↳ Feeding to animals:
– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: body cover of vermillion cinnabar

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– Yes

↳ How many humans are present:

– Number of human sacrifices: 5

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

–Other [specify]: I DO NOT KNOW

↳ Animal:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: no

↳ Other

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: none

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– No

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: no

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: none

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– I don't know

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: none

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: none

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: thousands presumably given the size of the public plaza spaces

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: we cannot reconstruct this from the inscriptions alone

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– Yes

↳ Adults

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Male

– Female

↳ Children

– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:

– Other/InD

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves

– No

↳ Elites

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: none

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: locals of Palenque according to isotopic profile

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Suicide

– I don't know

↳ Bloodletting

– Yes

↳ Mutilation
– I don't know

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expect of elites:
– Yes

↳ Is it an elite prerogative:
– No

↳ Is it a kingship prerogative:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– Yes

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: I do not know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
– Yes

↳ By all the community
– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Heirs

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The mausoleum and inner sanctuary was sealed and closed off during the century after construction.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written at this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they oral:
 - No
- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Housed within the place/structure:
 - Yes
- ↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: none

Bibliography

General References

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